

METHODS FOR DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF HYPERTROPHIC GINGIVITIS IN ADOLESCENTS**Imanov E.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor***Ibragimov E.***Doctor of Philosophy in Biology, Assistant**Department of Pediatry Dentistry***Huseynova R.***Department of Therapeutic Dentistry, Assistant**Azerbaijan Medical University**Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

Gum diseases remain one of the most pressing issues in modern dentistry, as the incidence of this pathology shows a steady upward trend. The high prevalence of periodontal diseases, the increasing number of children and young people with inflammatory oral diseases, and frequent relapses underscore the need for a deep study of the etiology and pathogenesis of these conditions. Moreover, there is a strong demand for more effective methods for prevention and treatment.

Keywords: adolescence, periodontal diseases, hypertrophic gingivitis.

In recent times, periodontal diseases have gained special importance, not only as a medical issue but also as a social problem. It has been established that initial changes in periodontal tissues are often observed as early as school age. According to WHO data, 80% of children in different countries suffer from periodontal diseases, with 90% of 12-year-olds having gingivitis. With age, the severity of the pathological process in periodontal tissues increases.

The development and course of periodontal diseases in adolescents have their own distinctive features. A decrease in luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) levels within physiological norms exacerbates the symptoms of chronic hypertrophic gingivitis in the presence of factors that worsen its course, such as a shallow oral vestibule, vertical incisal disocclusion, and the crowded position or abnormal positioning of certain teeth. Juvenile gingivitis can occur in girls one to one and a half years before the onset of menstruation.

The functioning of the immune system is governed by the neurohormonal system, which regulates metabolic and microcirculatory processes in the body. Biological substances, such as inhibitors like the natural inhibitory factor, humoral endogenous immunodepressants, and anti-immunoglobulins, play an essential role in maintaining homeostasis. Hormonal gingivitis is often accompanied by increased tooth mobility due to osteoporosis in the jawbone tissue. The prevalence and intensity of periodontal inflammatory reactions increase with age.

Despite the advancement in diagnostic methods, the disease is often diagnosed in its later stages. It is known that in adolescents and young people, the course of inflammatory periodontal diseases is particularly aggressive and resistant to treatment. Despite ongoing studies on this topic, the pathogenesis of inflammatory periodontal diseases in children and adolescents remains largely unclear. It is widely accepted that gingivitis and periodontitis arise from an inflammatory reac-

tion in the gums due to the pathogenic action of microorganisms. Over time, the inflammation becomes chronic, recurs, and eventually leads to the destruction of the gingival attachment, periodontal ligament, and resorption of the alveolar bone tissue.

Inflammation of periodontal tissues alters key biochemical and immunological parameters that characterize the level of the inflammatory process, tissue destruction in the oral cavity, and the degree of endogenous intoxication. These can be used as markers of the periodontal tissue condition and for assessing the effectiveness of treatment. Investigating these parameters in the treatment of periodontal diseases in children and adolescents is highly promising. The results of studies on the etiology and pathogenesis of periodontal diseases in children and adolescents are quite diverse. The roles of microbial, traumatic, immune, vascular, and other factors have been extensively studied. However, understanding the development of periodontal pathology requires knowledge of the balance between internal and external factors, as indicated by Arkovy in 1903.

The etiological factor almost never manifests itself as a single "specific culprit" and only one particular disease; it does not just act on the body, but interacts with it. The adolescent period is characterized by disproportionate and discordant development of the body and coincides with increased physical and intellectual loads, intensive mental activity, and high psycho-emotional stress. This leads to significant fluctuations in the activity levels of bodily systems, both within physiologically acceptable limits and beyond them. Specifically, there are overloads in the autonomic and endocrine systems, higher nervous activity, and emotional sphere, which, as a result, contribute to the onset of psychosomatic disorders. Against this background, both local and general unfavorable factors can cause both mild reactive changes and severe morphological disturbances in the periodontal tissues.

As a result, one of the current issues in adolescent clinical periodontology is the search for fundamentally new approaches to developing methods of differential

diagnosis of periodontal diseases, specifically in assessing changes in periodontal tissues depending on the condition of the body. Particularly important is the diagnosis of conditions that directly precede the clinical manifestation of diseases: functional (pre-disease) states on the border of normality and pathology, during which reversible changes are still possible.

With the development of dental technologies, new progressive methods are emerging to optimize the treatment process, improving the quality of life for patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases. At the present stage of dental development, the treatment of inflammatory periodontal diseases involves a comprehensive approach aimed at eliminating inflammatory processes in the periodontium, restoring the structural and functional properties of the periodontal complex elements, and enhancing both local and general defense factors. This is achieved through a combination of etiological, pathogenetic, and symptomatic therapies. Some authors note that the treatment period for periodontal disease patients is reduced after prescribing a complex of direct antioxidants, such as ascorbate, floculin, and vitamin E.

There are recommendations for including vitamins A, E, and K in comprehensive treatment for periodontal diseases. Among synthetic antioxidants, dibunol (iodinol) is the most thoroughly studied. It is an insoluble antioxidant in water, making parenteral administration impossible, and is applied locally in clinical practice. According to some data, dibunol normalizes blood circulation in periodontal tissues, inhibits lipid peroxidation (LPO), and has mild bactericidal and immunostimulating properties. As a result, it is recommended for use in periodontal practice for treating mild gingivitis and periodontitis. Effective forms of dibunol include 5% and 10% liniment, applications and dressings, and a 10% solution for phonophoresis. There is evidence of a good therapeutic effect when treating periodontitis with 20% gel of Precitina, a plant-derived bioflavonoid. The fastest effect was observed in the treatment of catarrhal gingivitis and exacerbation of mild chronic periodontitis.

Some researchers recommend using an antioxidant enzyme preparation for local gingivitis therapy. This preparation, derived from plant cell biomass, contains catalase, peroxidase, phospholipids, and trace elements. According to the literature, positive dynamics in clinical parameters of chronic periodontitis were observed as early as the second or third day after treatment with a biologically active supplement based on spirulina and chlorella, which contain antioxidant enzymes, catalase, and coenzyme Q10. Some authors have used this supplement as a gingival application twice a day for 10 days.

In modern dentistry, there is significant interest in treatment methods that provide a pronounced positive effect with minimal side effects. One such method is phytotherapy, which has become an officially recognized and rapidly developing method of treatment. The main advantages of phytotherapy over traditional methods include:

1. Plant-based medicines, used in phytotherapy, can have a complex effect on periodontal tissues due to

the presence of various biologically active substances, offering antiseptic, analgesic, bactericidal, bacteriostatic, anti-inflammatory, keratoplastic, and anti-edematous effects, among others.

2. Phytopreparations are low in toxicity, act gently, and rarely cause allergic reactions, allowing for their prolonged use (even for years) without harm to the patient, as resistance or adaptation does not develop.

3. Phytopreparations can be recommended for patients of all age groups.

4. An important advantage of plant medicines is their generally pleasant organoleptic properties.

5. Phytopreparations stimulate tissue regeneration processes.

In addition, medicinal plants have a positive effect on the macroorganism as a whole: they restore the normal microflora of the intestines, help eliminate dysbiosis, normalize the functioning of many internal organs, and enhance overall immunity.

Thus, the planning, implementation of treatment measures, and patient monitoring should be conducted comprehensively. Actions by dentists and general practitioners should focus on eliminating or reducing the influence of the symptom complex that contributes to the development of the pathological process.

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